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UNIVERSITY OF
DELAWARE

TURNEYES 892951

RESEARCHER ANNEMARIE WALTER
OUTGOING SUPERVISOR DAVID REDLAWSK
INCOMING SUPERVISOR CEES VAN DER EIJK

REPORT 13

PRESENTATION ANNUAL
MEETING OF THE MIDWEST
POLITICAL SCIENCE
ASSOCIATION, APRIL 13-16,
2023, CHICAGO, IL, UNITED
STATES

| November 2024

The project Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

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#2023 MPSA Annual Meeting

Priming Voters' Moral Identities in the Face of Politicians' Moral Transgressions

Annemarie Walter

David Redlawsk

Heon Lee

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Research Project

Research Question: How do voters' moral and partisan identities affect their responses to politicians' moral transgressions?

Aim: To disentangle the effect of these two identities on voters' responses to politicians' immoral behavior

Study: Set of survey-embedded experiments in which we prime voters' moral identity (or partisan) identities before exposure to different scenarios

Pre-test: Priming moral identity

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Moral Identity

Moral Reasoning

The capacity to make judgments about whether certain actions are right or wrong

Moral Identity

The importance (or salience) of morality to a person's identity

Moral Actions

Behavioral outcomes: e.g., motivations, moral commitments, moral conducts, emotional or attitudinal responses, etc.

001 >> A Character Perspective

- A trait-like tendency: the degree to which morality is central to one's identity (a sense of self) and unified with one's personal values and goals (Blasi 1983)

002 >> A Social Cognitive Perspective

- A network of cognitively accessible moral schemas: the extent to which one develops a robust network of chronically accessible moral schemas (Lapsley and Narvaez 2004)

Chronic and Temporal Accessibility

- **Internalization:** the extent to which people see moral traits as central to their sense of self
- Specific situations can temporally increase the accessibility of people's moral self-schema

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Moral Identity

A Self-reported Scale for Moral Identity

(Aquino and Reed 2002)

Present participants with a list of nine moral traits

Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Helpful, Hardworking, Honest, and Kind

Ask participants to visualize a person (or the self) with those traits and how that person would think, feel, and act

Have them rate their agreement with 10 statements:

5 for Internalization

The extent to which people see morality as central to their sense of the self.

5 for Symbolization

The extent to which people see themselves as outwardly displaying a moral identity to the world

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Data

A heterogeneous sample of 248 respondents recruited using Amazon MTurk

Respondents were all randomly assigned to one of three treatments

Respondents were later all exposed to the same scenario

Results for data as is and cleaned

Characteristics Respondents

Age	M= 37.29, SD= 17.43
Female	18.95%
Education	M= 4.10, SD= 1.09
Race	White 70.56%, Black 1.21%, Asian 6.85% Indian/Native 21.37%
Partisanship	Democrats 50.40%, Independents 4.03%, Republicans 45.56%
Liberal	M= 2.95, SD= 1.09
Religiosity	M= 3.53, SD= 1.40

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The Prime

(Aquino et al. 2007; Reed et al. 2016; Sanders et al. 2018; Wu and Yang 2018)

Q. The purpose of this exercise is to examine how people relate to the objects in their surroundings when telling stories about themselves.

Listed below are nine words in alphabetical order.

Treatment	Control A	Control B
Caring, Compassionate, Fair, Friendly, Generous, Helpful, Hardworking, Honest, and Kind N= 84	Book, Car, Chair, Computer, Desk, House, Pen, Street, and Table N= 86	Carefree, Compatible, Favorable, Generally, Happy, Harmless, Open-minded, Polite, and Respectable N= 78

Please take a few moments (about 5-10 seconds per word) to think about what each word means to you.

Please write a story or a few stories about yourself **using each word at least once.**

A Manipulation Check

How much do the stories you wrote reflect how you see yourself, no matter whether the item is true about you:

The story reflects me as a OOO ...

Participants in the moral prime condition reported that the story reflects more about them as moral persons than those in the non-primed condition A. But there is no significant difference between the prime and non-moral condition B.

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Respondents exposed to the moral prime reported significantly more that the story reflects them as a moral person than respondents exposed to control A. No significant difference between respondents exposed to the prime or control B was found.

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Does the treatment affect respondents' moral identity?

Mean of Moral Identity Scale by the Prime Conditions

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The Vignette

Moral Transgression

Next, we would like to have you consider an action of a politician that you might observe. Please read the statement very carefully and then answer the questions that follow it.

"Patrick Donovan is a 4-term state legislator planning to run again in the next election. He is 56 years old, married, and has two children. He attended the state university, and after graduation, he worked in the family business. You read an online news story about state politics. In the story, you learn about a report that Rep. Donovan laughed out loud at a homeless voter who asked for help."

DVs

1. How would you now rate him on the following characteristics? (on a 7-point scale)

Immoral / Incompetent / Unlikable / Weak leader / Untrustworthy / Uncompassionate.

2. How *inappropriate* is his behavior for a politician? (on a 5-point scale)

3. How *legally* wrong is it? (on a 5-point scale)

4. How *morally* wrong is it? (on a 5-point scale)

Does the treatment affect respondents' evaluations of the transgressor?

Mean of Evaluation Scores by Characteristics (Treat vs. Con A vs. Con B)

Does the treatment affect respondents' evaluations of the transgressor's behavior?

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What is the effect of moral identity on the evaluation of the transgressor across the conditions?

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Discussions

>> **A Dysfunctional Prime**

Despite utilizing a manipulation that has been effective in previous studies, the prime in this paper did not significantly increase the level of moral identity, and the findings on its impact on the evaluation of a moral transgressor were contradictory.

We would appreciate any comments or advice on how to manipulate moral identity as we prepare for the next steps.

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